

Training BoF @RSECon 2024

5 September 2025

Matt Craddock, Aman Goel, Pip Grylls, Juan Herrera, Toby Hodges, Emma Hogan, Olexandr Konovalov, Aleks Nenadic, Colin Sauze, Dimitrios Theodorakis, Philipp Thiele, Chris Wood

Motivation

- Unite training communities and people with common interest in training through a Special Interest Group (SIG) or other community activities
 - Provision of computational training for researchers and RSEs
 - Lesson and curricula development
 - Definition of skills, competencies and diverse progression pathways for RSEs to help track and manage their professional development and career progression, and knowledge within RSE groups
 - Applying for joint funding to support training activities
- Explore priorities around training needs and define a roadmap of activities
- Explore how we can leverage the support of the RSE Society
- Find effort within the community for taking the lead on identified activities

Background - Existing Efforts (UK)

- The UK Carpentries community and various local chapters
- [Satellite Training event at RSECon 2023](#): delivery of materials, development of materials, policy, culture, and resourcing for training in academia, developing RSEs to deliver training
- [UK RSE Competencies group](#)
 - Started at SSI Collaborations Workshop 2023, borrows from [BCS IT Skills Framework](#)
 - Part of the RSEToolkit, draft skills framework and website prototype
- [Met Office Science Professions Skills Framework](#)
- Local, regional or national RSE/library/data science/HPC groups, projects and institutions

de-RSE e.V. teachingRSE group

- Started @deRSE23 with a workshop
- Current work:
 - Paper: Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of an RSE <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.11457> (Feedback welcome!)
 - Website for material overview: <https://de-rse.org/learn-and-teach/>
- Starting/Upcoming:
 - Curriculum for an RSE Master in Germany (with German CS society)
 - Paper: Improving institutional/university education w.r.t. RSE skills
 - Paper: Call to Action for Germany

US-RSE Education & Training group

- Current work:
 - Seminar series: https://us-rse.org/wg/education_training/seminar_series/
 - Training resources: https://us-rse.org/wg/education_training/training/
 - Skill list: https://us-rse.org/wg/education_training/skills/
- Starting/Upcoming:
 - List of RSE Archetypes

Dutch eScience Centre (NeSC)

- [RSE role descriptions and job profiles](#)

What will the session look like

- **[20 minutes]** - Group discussion to identify areas/topics of interest for training that should be addressed with immediate priority
 - Using Padlet platform
 - 15 minutes individual input - add your sticky notes to Padlet, comment or +1 to existing notes
 - 5 minutes for session leads to consolidate the Padlet and identify 3 key/focus areas
- **[30 minutes]** Breakout groups: in-depth discussions on the 3 key areas
- **[15 minutes]** Reporting back and conclusions
 - Each group reports on the priorities for their topic/focus area
 - Identify people willing to be involved

<https://bit.ly/rsecon24-training-padlet>

Group-wide Discussion: Identify and vote for key areas

- <link & QR Code to Miro board>

Breakout Groups

- [Breakout 1](#): Topic 1 (breakout chairs - ...)
- [Breakout 2](#): Topic 2 (breakout chairs - ...)
- [Breakout 3](#): Topic 3 (breakout chairs - ...)

[Breakout 1](#)

[Breakout 2](#)

[Breakout 3](#)

Reporting Back

- Priorities for breakout groups

SocRSE SIG Proposal - Expression of Interest

- <https://bit.ly/rsecon24-training-form>

Thank you for participating!